

MODELING THE VISCOSITY AND CONVERSION OF IN-SITU POLYMERIZING PBT USING EMPIRICAL DATA

M. Steeg^{1*}, P. Mitschang¹, P. Chakraborty¹, and T. Hartmann²

¹Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH

Erwin-Schrödinger-Straße, Geb. 58

67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany

markus.steeg@ivw.uni-kl.de

²Cyclics Europe GmbH

European Headquarters

Naundorfer Straße VIZ 118

01987 Schwarzheide, Germany

SUMMARY

Heading towards faster cycle times for continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastic parts, highly viscous matrices and densely packed textile structures hinder the breakthrough. To overcome these limitations, reactive polymers, such as Cyclic Butylene Terephthalate (CBT[®]) make a contribution having very low processing viscosities. Modeling viscosity and conversion are performed on an empirical data base.

Keywords: Manufacturing, polymer matrix composites, thermoplastic FRPC, reactive polymer, Cyclic Butylene Terephthalate, CBT[®], PBT, GPC, modeling, viscosity, kinetics, conversion, rheology, dielectric analysis, isothermal modeling, non-isothermal modeling

MOTIVATION

Rapid manufacturing of continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites is limited to boundary conditions. High melting viscosities, ranging from 100 Pa·s to 10000 Pa·s, and dense packed textile structures are slowing down the fiber wet-out [1-3]. Advanced stiffness and strength to weight correlation is driven by fiber length, fiber orientation, and fiber volume fraction [1, 4, 5]. Improvements will increase permeability but slow down the impregnation of each fiber filament. One strategy to accelerate process speed is based on minimizing the distance from polymer to filaments during impregnation and consolidation. Film stacking, powder impregnation, or the use of pre-impregnated semi-finished products are the technologies in use [1, 5, 6]. On the other hand it is possible to work on matrix modification [7, 8]. Reactive polymers minimize the level of viscosity [9-11]. Based on low molecular monomer or oligomer groups, with 10⁵-times lower viscosity, the in-situ polymerization takes place in the manufacturing step [12]. Consequently, the viscosity and conversion to high molecular macromolecules have to be studied for designing manufacturing technologies.

MATERIAL

Cyclic Butylene Terephthalate (CBT[®]) is a cyclic oligomer that polymerizes in presents of temperature and catalyst to the well known technical polymer

Polybutylterephthalate (PBT)¹. The polyaddition to pCBT is an entropically-driven athermic ring-opening process [7, 13-15]. Prior to processing and testing the moisture content should be reduced but there is no need to have inert atmosphere.

CBT[®]160 consists of a mixture of CBT[®]100 resin (Cyclics Europe GmbH, Schwarzheide, Germany) and catalyst FASCAT 4101 (Arkema GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany). Pure oligomers CBT[®]100 and one-component pre-mixture CBT[®]160 resins are commercially available as pellets. In case of CBT[®]160, the catalyst, which converts the cyclic Polybutylterephthalate to PBT, is already compounded into the resin allowing an easy and fast catalysis after melting to >180°C [7, 13].

Figure 1: Exemplarily summary of 9 batches of CBT[®] 160 resin, out of Cyclics Europe GmbH 2009 production, and the corresponding average molecular weight

Figure 2 shows a typical DSC thermogram of CBT[®]160 for two heating cycles at heating and cooling rates of 20 K/min. During the 1st heating the CBT[®]160 oligomers melt in the range of 140 °C up to 185 °C. No broad exothermic polymerization peak could be found. In contrast to, e.g. in-situ polymerization of lactam 12, it is not possible to monitor or derive the reaction kinetics with heat flow models [16-18].

$$\frac{\partial \beta}{\partial t} = \frac{\frac{\partial H}{\partial t}}{\Delta H}$$

The isothermal crystallization temperature T_c for pCBT varies around 190 °C. Behaviors and modeling surrounding crystallization could be found in [19, 20].

Melting of pCBT is indicated through the last endothermic peak among a melting point of approx. 220 °C.

¹ Denote pCBT = polymerized CBT[®]160. The chemical structure equates to PBT

Figure 2: DSC data for CBT[®]160, 2 heating cycles

EMPERICAL DATA – MEASURING

Rheology

For testing rheological behavior an Ares (Rheometric Scientific Inc.) plate–plate configuration was used. The procedure for measurement was as follows: The right amount of CBT[®]160 powder was pre-confectioned in form of pressed tablets. All tablets were dried for 8-12 hours at 80 °C in order to reduce water content less than 200 ppm. The temperature chamber was pre-heated to an isothermal temperature. One tablet was placed between the aluminum plates with a diameter of 25 mm. Uniform handling in sense of time for inserting the tablets is essential for consistent results. Subsequently, the vertical adjustment for the transducer unit followed. The gap was positioned to a height of approx. 1 mm. Dynamic viscosity (η_{dyn}), loss-, storage modulus, and torque was recorded as function of time and temperature. The shear rate was kept constant at 40 rad/s. Automatic strain adjustment was set to 80 % with a decrease of 10 %, and maximum torque was set to 100 g·cm. Figure 3 shows the viscosity characteristics of classical PBT (BASF, Ludwigshafen, Germany Ultradur 6550) and CBT[®]160 at three different temperatures.

At constant shear rate the dynamic viscosity of PBT at 250 °C is around 1000 Pa·s. The reactive CBT[®]160 polymerizes and crystallizes below 195 °C in the solid phase (energy elastic state). Minimum viscosity is affected by isothermal temperature. At 170 °C dynamic viscosity reaches 0.3 Pa·s and at 195 °C the global minimum of 0.015 Pa·s is accomplished [9]. Clear off 220 °C CBT[®]160 polymerizes in the molten pCBT phase (entropy elastic state). Minimum dynamic viscosity (approx. 0.015 Pa·s) could not be detected because it has already passed through during setting up the rheometer and transient oscillation. After the kinetics took place the dynamic viscosity equates the level of classical PBT around 1000 Pa·s.

Figure 3: Viscosity of CBT[®]160 and PBT

Viscosities for CBT[®]160 were taken from 150 °C to 260 °C in intervals of 10 °C. From 180 °C to 200 °C the interval was measured every 5 °C. All rheological measurements were repetitively carried out two times for every isothermal condition.

Gel Permeation Chromatography

For determination of molecular weights of PBT and conversion of CBT[®] to pCBT a conventional Agilent HPLC (1100 series, isocratic pump, degasser, autosampler, UV detector) equipped with two Phenomenex PhenogelTM 5 μ linear (300 mm x 7.8 mm) columns was used. Alternatively, special high resolution columns worked well for a better peak separation. The polymers were prepared as follows: 4.75 g of pure CBT[®]100 was mixed with 0.25 g of catalyst (or 5 g of CBT[®]160). From this mixture 0.5 g were filled in a test-tube and connected to a vacuum manifold. The materials were dried for 30 min at 80 °C under vacuum. The polymerization was performed at 190 °C for 30 min under vacuum. To stop the reaction, all test-tubes are placed immediately into an ice bath and samples were taken for the GPC analysis.

GPC conditions: A 95 % / 5 % mixture of chloroform and HFIP (1,1,1,3,3,3-Hexafluoro-2-propanol) was used as eluent. Different polystyrene standards between 2970 and 2061000 g/mol are suited for calibration. The GPC operates at 1 ml/min at 40 °C column temperature, the injection volume is 1 μ l, all peaks are detected at 254 nm and the runtime is 27 min. All data and figures shown in this article were generated using the PhenogelTM columns. For analysis the Agilent ChemStation software extended with a specific GPC add-on is used.

Determination of molecular weights: After polymerization of CBT[®]160 to pCBT a small crushed sample of ~30-70 mg was dissolved in a 1 ml mixture of CH₂Cl₂ / HFIP (75 % / 25 %) at 70 °C. After complete dissolving 3 ml of chloroform and a few micro liters of oDCB as internal standard were added to the solution followed by filtration into a HPLC vial through a 0.45 μ m filter.

Figure 4 shows a typical GPC chromatogram of pure cyclic oligomers (CBT[®]100) including oDCB as internal standard (line graph). Partial catalysis to pCBT (M_w = 126280 g/mol, conversion = 88.5 %) illustrates the GPC separation between educt and product (dashed graph).

Figure 4: GPC chromatogram of CBT[®]100 and catalysis to pCBT160

MODELING

Strategy

As conversion from CBT[®] to pCBT could not be derived from thermal analysis the strategy to find isothermal conversion data is oriented backwards from the polymerized product. Therefore, CBT[®]160 is polymerized in an oven under isothermal conditions. Specimens were taken out of the oven, quenched down in ice water at different polymerization times (t_{poly}), and dried again. A following GPC analysis gave information about molecular weight (M_w) and conversion. The goal was to transfer the isothermal conversion into an Arrhenius model and compute kinetic parameters with minimum error. Subsequently, the model could be transferred into a non-isothermal model for prediction of any temperature-time profile occurring in manufacturing processes.

Figure 5 illustrates an extract of raw conversion data from over 200 single GPC measurements performed under isothermal conditions. All further modeling is based on this data.

Figure 5: Conversion data for isothermal polymerization captured from GPC

We planed to subdivide the whole modeling process in four coherent parts. First we modeled the isothermal conversion to predict the kinetic parameters. This availed us to extend up to an analytical conversion model for the non-isothermal conversion. Then we proposed our isothermal viscosity model that directly uses the conversion model and extend it further for a non-isothermal condition.

Modeling Isothermal Conversion

In the previous section one should have noticed the asymptotic behavior of the conversion profiles at different isotherms. Keeping this dynamics in mind the chemical reaction kinetics involved in this process will be simulated using the following first order ordinary differential equation model [17, 21, 22].

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dn(t)}{dt} &= -k(T)n(t) \\ n(t_0) &= n_0 \end{aligned}$$

The k in this equation is the so called rate constant that follows the Arrhenius equation.

$$k(T) = ve^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}} \text{ where } \begin{cases} E_a \text{ is activation energy} \\ R \text{ is the universal gas constant} \\ v \text{ is the pre-factor} \end{cases}$$

As k will be constant throughout a certain isothermal condition the solution to the above equation can be written as: $n(t) = n_0 \exp(-kt)$. We model the isothermal conversion as

$$\alpha(t) = 1 - n(t) \text{ with } n_0 = 1.$$

After fitting the above non-linear model to the empirical isothermal conversion data we got the rate constant at different temperatures shown in Figure 6. Average squared error is < 0.2 .

Figure 6: Modeling isothermal GPC data with first order ordinary differential equation model

The predicted rate constant values are discretely transferred in the Arrhenius plot $\{1/T, \log(k)\}$ and kinetic parameters (E_a, ν) are recovered through a linear regression with an average squared error of < 0.16 1/s. For CBT[®]160 according to Figure 7 E_a is 70.4 kJ/mol, and pre-factor is $3.15 \cdot 10^5$ 1/s. This enabled us to predict the time dependent rate constant.

Figure 7: Arrhenius plot for CBT[®]160

Modeling Non-isothermal Conversion

In a non-isothermal condition the previous formula can not be used. Conversion modeling needs to modify the $\alpha(t)$ in a different way as the governing differential equation will change when we incorporate the time/temperature dependent reaction rate. However, assuming a linear time-temperature ramp then it is possible to deduce from the corresponding reaction as an exact formula of conversion.

$$\alpha(t) = 1 - \exp \left(\frac{v \left(E_a \text{Ei} \left(-\frac{E_a}{RT_0} \right) + RT_0 \exp \left(-\frac{E_a}{RT_0} \right) \right)}{R\beta} - \frac{v \left(E_a \text{Ei} \left(-\frac{E_a}{R(t\beta + T_0)} \right) + R(t\beta + T_0) e^{-\frac{E_a}{R(t\beta + T_0)}} \right)}{R\beta} \right)$$

where $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} T_0 \text{ (Starting temperature)} \\ \beta \text{ (Linear heating rate)} \\ \text{Ei}(z) = -\int_{-z}^{\infty} e^{-t} / t \, dt \end{array} \right.$

Other than the usual ones the new symbols are described within the equation. Modeling the continuous time-temperature profiles used in manufacturing is far more complicated than a linear temperature-time ramp so we will prefer to numerically solve the differential equation model and then predict the conversion process. Figure 8 shows two conversion profiles that were simulated corresponding to two different time-temperature profiles used in continuous manufacturing. We notice from the simulation that for a comparatively fast heating rate and less holding time we failed to achieve full conversion. Simulated conversion results were proven within standard deviation of three GPC measurements taken from the produced fiber-reinforced polymer composites that were tested after production.

Figure 8: T-t-profile from continuous manufacturing and modeled conversion

Modeling Dynamic Viscosity

The main idea while modeling the dynamic viscosity (η_{dyn}) was to track its behavior just by correlating it with predicted conversion at different time points of the time-temperature profile coming from manufacturing. As the primary interest is in the lowest viscosity region of CBT[®]160, the approach specially focuses to pick the lowest bump of the dynamic viscosity profile in a log-log plane. In an isothermal condition it is possible to consider our model as a “*bipartite*” model. One part predicts the melting down part of CBT[®]160 and the other one predicts the increasing part of the viscosity profile. In the second part our model converges with the model proposed by Luisier [17]. While extending our model to non-isothermal condition it becomes far more complicated than its simple bipartite form. It acts as a union of multiple bipartite models each predicting the viscosity at a unique point of the time-temperature profile.

$$\Phi_1(t, T) = \begin{cases} \exp\left(\log(\eta_{\max}) + \frac{\alpha(t)(\varepsilon(T) - \log(\eta_{\max}))}{c_1(T)}\right), & \text{for } \alpha(t) \leq c_1(T) \\ \exp(\varepsilon(T)), & \text{for } \alpha(t) > c_1(T) \end{cases}$$

$$\Phi_2(t, T) = \exp(a(T) + b(T)\alpha(t))$$

$$\eta(t, T) = \begin{cases} \Phi_1(t, T), & \text{for } \alpha(t) \leq c_2(T) \\ \Phi_2(t, T), & \text{for } \alpha(t) > c_2(T) \end{cases}$$

In the model shown above there are three very important parameters that are temperature dependent or in other words time dependent when we have an explicit time to temperature correspondence. We call c_1 and c_2 as “*turning parameter*” and ε is the “*depth decider*”. The turning parameters detect the melting region of the viscosity profile and depth decider is meant to track the minimum in the log-log plane $\{\log(t), \log(\eta(t))\}$. In the model we denote viscosity of CBT[®] at semi-crystalline solid state as η_{\max} around 400000 Pa·s.

Figure 9: Matching of isothermal viscosity profiles

Figure 10: Predicting non-isothermal viscosity profile

Figure 9 and Figure 10 show the validation of our model. The model successfully tracks the lowest dip of the dynamic viscosity profile. From the distribution of the three important parameters c_1 , c_2 , and ε over temperature we noticed a nontrivial dynamics. We also notice that model is considerably sensitive to these parameters. Due to having sparse isothermal data that does not pass through all intermediate temperature the commonly used third order spline interpolation of these parameters resulted into unexpected oscillation. We used piecewise linear Bezier interpolation and it resulted in a much expected improvement.

SUMMARY

Conversion and viscosity of cyclic oligomers (CBT[®]160) was measured using GPC equipment and rheometer. An isothermal Arrhenius based conversion model, forecasting the ring-opening conversion from oligomer to polymer (pCBT = PBT), was derived and optimized from GPC results. The isothermal conversion model was extended up to an analytical conversion model for non-isothermal conditions. Simulated results were validated successfully.

Furthermore, it was possible to create a direct link between conversion data and dynamic viscosity. Again the results were validated and optimized by means of isothermal rheological measurements. Finally, it was possible to generate a model that predicts conversion and dynamic viscosity for every thermal condition.

This modeling will lead to accurate prediction and design for high speed manufacturing processes for FRPC with CBT[®] in various technologies.

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